

Final Report ^a

Entwicklung und Vermessung von sehr dicken aerodynamischen Profilen für Windturbinenblätter ^b

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1 Introduction (all)

Wind energy is a crucial component of the ongoing energy transition and plays a significant role in the electricity supply of Germany [13]. Among renewable energy sources, wind energy offers the most promising and cost-effective expansion potential in the short to medium term [12]. Particularly in northern Germany, it serves as a primary energy supplier and presents ample opportunities for meeting future demands, such as the competitive production of green hydrogen [34].

Over the past three decades, advancements in wind energy technology have been substantial, largely attributed to the efforts of German scientists and companies. These advancements have resulted in significant reductions in specific electricity production costs, improved overall plant performance, and enhanced efficiency [27]. However, in order to further enhance energy conversion efficiency and due to the state of the art already achieved, it has become necessary to focus on optimizing rather minor details that were not previously seriously considered. One such detail is the transition area located around 20 % of the relative blade length, which encompasses the initial 20 % of the blade length near the rotor hub. This area is highlighted in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Rotor blade of a wind turbine with the root region highlighted.

Until now, the design of this particular area has primarily focused on meeting structural, i.e., the load-bearing requirements, neglecting the importance of aerodynamic considerations. One of the main reasons for this oversight is the lack of suitable development tools for creating aerodynamically efficient profiles for relatively "thick" geometries, such as the one observed in this case. Consequently, undesired flow separations frequently occur within this region, resulting in unfavorable down-force and high drag instead of the desired lift and low resistance. To illustrate this point, consider the following rhetorical example: achieving a lift coefficient (c_L) of 1 and a drag coefficient (c_D) below 0.01 is desirable, while a negative c_L and a c_D of 1 are highly undesirable.

1.1 Objectives

The objective of this research project is to investigate the possibilities and effects of aerodynamically optimizing a specific section within the transition area of the rotor blade. This section is located approximately halfway between the blade root and the beginning of the conventionally aerodynamically profiled region.

Specifically, the aim is to examine a profile with a relative thickness of 60 %, which represents the ratio of the maximum profile thickness to the profile depth (compare the values marked in yellow in Fig. 2). A relative thickness of 100 % for example corresponds to a cylinder. It is worth noting that currently, only mature profiles up to a relative thickness of about 40 % are available in the existing state of the art.

Although investigations have been conducted on thicker profiles in previous EU projects [36], none of them have specifically explored a large thickness of 60 % as targeted in this project. Additionally, the Danish Technical University (DTU) has introduced the DTU-FFA-W-600 profile [21], which, however, also exhibits undesired down-force according to preliminary analyses.

Figure 2: Profile geometry - 1: Zero-lift line; 2: Leading edge; 3: Nose circle; 4: Max. thickness; 5: Camber; 6: Upper surface; 7: Trailing edge; 8: Camber mean-line; 9: Lower surface. Source: McCormick (1999) [20]

Within the project, several airfoil profiles with a 60 % relative thickness for the inner region segment are developed and analyzed using numerical methods. The criteria and methodologies for designing such innovative thick aerodynamic profiles are collaboratively developed by the project partners. The most promising aerodynamic profiles are subjected to detailed numerical computational fluid dynamic (CFD) simulations. Subsequently, the profile exhibiting the most favorable properties is manufactured as a physical model and tested in a wind tunnel to validate its characteristics and parameters. To facilitate efficient validation, recent advances in thermographic methods are employed to detect flow separation, complemented by the collection of pressure sensor data along the chord.

It should be acknowledged that the study of these highly thick profiles presents significant challenges from both simulation and measurement perspectives. To address these challenges, an experienced consortium consisting of Aerovide GmbH, Rendsburg (formerly aerodyn Energiesysteme GmbH), Deutsche WindGuard Engineering GmbH, Bremerhaven, and the Kiel University of Applied Sciences, renowned for their expertise in flow simulation and wind tunnel measurements, collaborate on this project.

2 Methodology (all)

Designing a new aerodynamic profile is mostly done as an iterative process, usually with a lot of flow simulation until a state is reached ready for testing in a wind tunnel. For ideal flow (no viscous effects included, no turbulent flow within the boundary layer of the profile) a one-to-one correspondence exists between the local static pressure and the geometrical shape [8], so that an *inverse (design) mode* is possible. Nevertheless, one has to know in advance which $c_p(x)$ is desirable to reach the design goals. A readable example is presented in [32] describing to design process for S809.

2.1 Known profiles of large thickness

Fig 3 shows three earlier designed aerodynamic profiles, which mainly resulted from simple up-scaling of thickness from older, less thick (around 40 %) ones. As can be immediately seen, a thin (< 2 % of chord) trailing edge (TE) is not at all appropriate, so profiles with pronounced trailing-edge (TE) - or flat-back - are necessary. They were investigated early in [33]. Comparable profiles from the FX (Franz Xaver Wortmann)-family were even used as early as for GROWIAN 2MW prototype [2]. As a final remark, it may be interesting to know that even before WWII Hoerner in 1939 [10](page 2-9) reported on measurements of a 70% thick strut in a water-tunnel with pronounced region of negative lift-slope. Recently Zhen Pei et al.[25] investigated an 60% profile as well which very much resembles the AE60 (see below) profile.

Figure 3: Earlier known profiles of 60 % thickness

2.2 Geometric interpolation (AE60) (VK)

Typically, any wind turbine blade has a circular hub so there must be some interpolation from the last profile (in many cases around 40 % thickness by today) to a circle. An example is given in Fig. 4. This profile as all given above show unwanted negative lift at moderate AOAs, see Fig 5.

2.3 Geometric design (BAL, WZX, APS)

Using a slightly more advanced but still engineering approach camber- and thickness-lines can be prescribed together with leading edge radius and trailing edge thickness and are then transferred to a shape with continuous curvature. This had been done for nine BAL (= Brandon Arthur Lobo) shapes, see Fig. 7. However, due to restrictions from manufacturing (see section 4) most of them had to be discarded.

One special point to be addressed from the beginning was to avoid negative lift and lift-slope as observed in an investigation of a symmetrical, profile-like shape [28]. This unwanted behaviour was confirmed when a simple interpolated profile (see Fig 4) was investigated in the very beginning underlining the need for newly developed profiles.

2.4 BAL002 and BAL003 (BAL)

According to the evaluations with BAL003 in a blade design by aerovide, the c_P (power coefficient - efficiency) could be improved by up to 3.8% and AEP by up to 2.1% with a 7.5m/s of the averaged wind speed. The aerodynamic benefit is obvious. However, the geometric shape fits not completely smoothly with the neighboring airfoil (DU00-W2-401) and the final cylindrical shape close to the hub. These concerns resulted in another approach, see section 2.5.

2.5 Design based on DU00-W2-401 (WZX)

Firstly, DU00-W2-40 as given is up-scaled with increased relative thickness of 60% (D60A), and then the relative thickness of the flatback is increased from 1% to 35% (D60B-V1). The geometry is smoothed using c_p (pressure) distribution (D60B-V2). Geometric compatibility was further improved by reducing the concave shape on the pressure side near the trailing edge (D60B-V3). After some c_p and geometry smoothing procedure, a new geometry (D60B-V5) is developed,

Figure 4: Geometric interpolations between a circle (at hub) and last profile (DU00-W2-401). Blue: linear interpolation based only on thickness; Red: spline interpolation for 2D-surface; Green: improved version. Last two provided by aerovide.

Figure 5: Negative lift for profile from Fig 4 at moderate AOAs

Figure 6: c_L vs c_D (polar) for profile from Fig 4

Figure 7: Engineering Design of nine (BAL) airfoils of 60 % thickness

Figure 8: CFD for BAL003: c_L vs AOA

Figure 9: CFD for BAL003: c_D vs AOA

Figure 10: Geometry of protected REpower(Senvion, Siemens) profile RE-W-70%-B9, based on FX79-W-660A [2]

and further investigated by CFD. The aerodynamic performance is comparable with BAL003, and the geometry is expected to be more friendly.

An effort is made to reduce the thickness of the flatback as 20%. Two ways are considered: round corner of the flatback (D60C-V1) and direct reduction of the flatback (D60C-V2). The simulation results of D60C-V1 show that the round corner on the pressure side decreases the C_l with about 0.2 for every AoA. D60C-V2 is not a successful modification with cL_{max} only ca. 1.0.

3 Patent Search (APS)

An extensive research on existing patents was performed see tables 8 and 9. The results were somewhat surprising, as many shapes of interest seem to be already protected [26, 30], see Fig. 10. This may not cause any problems if only scientific investigations were performed, but not to prevent possible commercial use it was decided to design new shapes *free from any third-party rights*.

4 Implications due to Manufacturability (VK)

4.1 Non-aerodynamic requirements

For each rotor blade section, a balance must be found between at least the following issues:

- aerodynamic requirements
- geometric compatibility
- structure requirements
- production requirements
- noise requirements

Figure 11: By integration of the BAL003 airfoil (blue marked section) into an existing rotor blade, significant undulations appear. Hence, the BAL003 airfoil is not matching well with the surrounding geometry.

For the transition area from the cylindrical blade root to the maximum chord area the noise requirements may be negligible. In this project the following issues need to be considered for the 60% thick flat-back airfoil:

- airfoil needs to fit well to surrounding airfoil sections, smooth splines, minimum undulations or fluctuations
- max thickness position preferably between 25% and 40% chord, optimum approx. $0.35c$
- high flapwise stiffness and sufficient space for the main spar caps
- preferably circular contour at leading edge to reduce variation of the mould separation line
- as much curvature as possible in the trailing edge buckling fields for maximum buckling stiffness
- angle of the flatback adjustable for production optimization and demoulding of the blade
- high maximum lift coefficient ≥ 1.5 , the higher the better
- efficiency (CL/CD) as high as possible
- aerodynamic coefficients insensitive to flatback height and flatback angle
- roughness insensitivity (smooth vs tripped)

The BAL003 airfoil offers very good aerodynamic properties, but according figure 11 it does not match well the non-aerodynamic requirements. Therefore, the geometry is shifted to a more conventional airfoil design with better compatibility to the surrounding airfoils. In figure 12 this more conventional airfoil is implemented in an existing blade. To improve the producibility and for an easier demoulding of the blade, the flatback angle is adjusted according to figure 13. This flatback adjustment reduces the aerodynamic properties to some extent, but the non-aerodynamic requirements are very well matched.

5 Numerical Simulation (BL, APS)

5.1 Xfoil, MSES

In this research project, numerical simulations were conducted using tools such as XFOIL and/or MSES to preliminary analyze and evaluate the performance of several 60 % thickness airfoil profiles developed for the targeted section within the transition area of the rotor blade. This

Figure 12: The blue marked airfoil is fitting much better to the surrounding blade geometry. However the trailing edge angle does not match well with the outer trailing edge angles, which is unfavorable for the demoulding of the blade.

Figure 13: The blue marked airfoil is fitting much better to the surrounding blade geometry. However the trailing edge angle does not match well with the outer trailing edge angles, which is unfavorable for the demoulding of the blade.

allowed for quick iterations and optimizations of the developed profiles. It must be noted that even though these tools are not designed to be used on profiles with thick trailing edges or on thick profiles as those analyzed here, they are sufficient to provide initial feedback on the developed profiles.

XFOIL was developed by Mark Drela at MIT [4], is widely recognized for its capability in airfoil analysis and design. MSES [5], on the other hand, is a collection of programs for the analysis and design of single- or multi-element airfoils based on the Euler equations for predicting the aerodynamic behavior. Although a detailed documentation of equations used is missing, it is known that viscous effects are included by integral boundary layer methods [6]. To some extent Xfoil was modified by van Rooij [37] to RFOIL.

The primary objective at this step was to assess the aerodynamic characteristics, particularly the lift and drag coefficients of the newly developed airfoil profiles. Based on the data obtained from the numerical simulations using XFOIL and MSES, plots illustrating the lift and drag characteristics of the developed airfoil profiles were generated. These plots serve as visual representations of the aerodynamic performance and provide a comparative analysis of the different airfoil designs. By examining the lift and drag data, the project aimed to identify the most promising airfoil profiles for further investigation and potential implementation in wind turbine blades.

5.2 2D-CFD - RANS

In the subsequent stage, the selected airfoil profiles were subjected to further analysis using Ansys FLUENT [24] and TAU [16] as computational tools. This analysis focused on employing the Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) CFD methodology to gain insights into the aerodynamic performance of the selected profiles. At this stage only two-dimensional (2D) RANS CFD was utilized for the evaluation of lift and drag polars. The simulations employed transitional CFD models and were conducted in both steady and transient conditions primarily for a chord based Reynolds number of 2M. The profile chosen for manufacture and a subsequent wind tunnel test was also evaluated at a chord based Reynolds number of 3M.

The resulting lift and drag data provided valuable insights into the aerodynamic performance of the profiles, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of their suitability for practical implementation in wind turbine blades. It is important to note that the RANS CFD simulations facilitated a more realistic representation of the flow than XFOIL or MSES but still depends on CFD models, for example, for the prediction of a transition location.

The data obtained from these simulations formed a critical basis for the selection of the airfoil profiles. The lift and drag characteristics provided insights into the performance of the profiles under varying flow conditions, aiding in the identification of the most favorable designs for subsequent stages of the project.

5.3 3D-CFD

The airfoil DU60B-V5 was implemented into a generic 10 MW wind turbine rotor blade for use in 3D-RANS calculations. See table 1 for main numbers.

1. Rated power: 10 MW
2. Rotor diameter: 200 m
3. Blade length: 98 m
4. Hub diameter 2 m
5. v-tip: 90 m/s ($N = 8.6$ RPM)
6. Airfoil: from DU-family
7. TSR-rated: 9.5

Table 1: Main figures of generic CIG10MW blade

Figure 14: Comparison of simulated 2D polar from 3 codes: c_L vs AOA

Figure 15: As Fig 14 but measurements included

Figure 16: Comparison of simulated 2D polar from 3 codes: c_D vs AOA

The profile was located at a span-wise radius of $x_m = 0.17$ as seen in Fig. 17. In addition, Fig 18 shows the polars of all profiles used.

As the new profile operates in the very inner part, so-called 3D effects [27] may be likely. Fig 20 shows a comparison auf sectional tangential forces at rated conditions. It can be seen that for $r < 30$ m BEM and 3D-CFD shows rather different results: Much more positive tangential forces producing more power. Compared to global c_p -values, CFD gives 0.490 ± 0.001 , almost equal to BEM (0.485).

An important task possible to check in 3D-CFD concerns to know if angle-of-attack is not spoiled by 3D effects. To estimate it we have chosen the so-called *inverse-BEM*-method [18], which is known not to be the most accurate but by far the most easiest to implement. A typical set of data for rated conditions (TSR = 9.5, pitch = 0° is presented in table 2. Surprisingly,

case	AOA	c_L	c_D	a	a'
KSS R=20	7.0	1.00	0.045	0.34	
FLUENT	6.1	1.104	0.038	0.42	-0.042

Table 2: Sample results for quasi-2D airfoil data from invBEM at $\omega = 0.99$, $v_{wind} = 11$ m/s at $r = 20$ m

3D-CFD gives higher induction, but somewhat lower AOA and higher c_L

To summarize, all efficiencies predicted by BEM and/or CFD are listed in table 3.

case	cP_{max}	ΔcP in %
AE60(spline)	0.468	
AE60(linear)	0.476	1.7
W570	0.480	2.5
BAL003	0.486	3.8
D60B-V5 (BEM)	0.485	3.6
D60B-V5 (CFD)	0.490	4.7
D60B-V5 (meas.)	0.488	4.3

Table 3: Comparison of cP_{max} improvement when using various profiles. It should be noted that various BEM-codes were used; among others also KSS [14]

Last three rows contain a collection of all data concerning improvement, esp. measurements (see section 6.4). An improvement of $4.20\% \pm 0.56\%$ in terms of c_P therefore is predicted. Very

Figure 17: Location of newly developed 60 % profile inside a generic CIG10MW blade and compared to a recently published 22MW reference wind turbine blade [38]

Figure 18: Used Polars for CIG10MW blade, D60B is presented in simulated and measured form as well as an 57 % thick airfoil, see table 3

Figure 19: Radial distribution of lift coefficient

Figure 20: Comparison of radial distribution of tangential (driving) forces. BEM (KSS and WZX-A) vs. 3D-RANS. Esp. in the part from where the 60% profile ($r < 17m$) start, pronounced (positive changes are visible)

Figure 21: Chord distribution of CIG10MW and IEA-22MW reference wind turbine

recently an open-access design of a 22MW, 282 m rotor-diameter, off-shore machine was released [38], in line with older 5MW and 10MW versions. However, we used an own design, more suited for specific for use in state-of-the-art commercial wind turbines. The very different design is obvious from Figs. 21 and 22.

Kremer [15] by using a somewhat smaller blade of 75 m length reports a c_P -max increase of 1.2 % only.

Figure 22: Twist distribution of CIG10MW and IEA-22MW reference wind turbine

Figure 23: Experimental set-up.

6 Wind Tunnel entry (NB, JS, APS)

6.1 Set-up

The wind tunnel is of the closed-circuit type, and can be operated either with an open (OTS) or a closed (CTS) test section. The closed test section is possible due to the use of a second nozzle and a modular test section system. For 2D airfoil tests the wind tunnel is operated with a rectangular 2.75 m x 1.25 m x 5 m (W x H x L) closed test section. The use of wall pressure measurements (WP), airfoil surface pressure (PP) measurements, force balances (FB) and a wake rake (WR) provides the necessary equipment for aerodynamic airfoil characterization. Wind Tunnel calibration including standard correction methods are described in [9, 35, 7]. Static surface pressure was measured by *HTD series - digital differential pressure sensors* from FirstSensor® and data is by a *CompaqDAQ-Module* from National Instruments. Sampling rate is 10 Hz and integration time (for each AOA) was 25 secs. The thermographic equipment consists of a ImageIR®8300 by INFRATEc. As the tunnel-entry run took one week (five working days), reproducibility could be checked each day by using the clean model. A more complete and detailed description is given in [7]. Fig. 23 shows the airfoil model mounted in the wind-tunnel.

One week wind tunnel entry took place in July 2023. Location of pressure ports as manufactured by Glasfaser Flugzeug-Service GmbH (Streifeneder) are shown in Fig. 24.

Some general information about the wind-tunnel and more specific information regarding our measurement is shown in [22, 23]. Numerically the wind tunnel was investigated earlier in [19, 17]. A sample histogram showing TI (0.23%) (at 70 m/s) is shown in Fig 25.

Figure 24: Location of pressure ports

Figure 25: Histogram of wind speed at 70 m/s inflow

6.2 Wind Tunnel Calibration and Corrections

Wind tunnel calibration [3] and correction are particularly important when investigating very thick airfoils as the one designed by us. More specific information can be found in:

- AGARD: Quality Assessment for Wind Tunnel Testing, 1994, [1]
- AGARD: Wind Tunnel Wall Corrections, 1998, [9]
- MSc thesis Lippert, numerical replica of DWGE's wind tunnel, 2014, [19]
- AIAA-2915-2577 ENERCON paper, 2015, [17]
- Paper on *corrections and uncertainties*, 2020, [35]
- DWAA flat plate calibration [22]
- specifics [23]

6.3 Test Matrix

In appendix 3, see section 12, the complete test-matrix is shown.

6.4 Results

In total, data corresponding to 33 polars was collected, including a lot of *more or less standard aerodynamic devices* like Vortex Generators, Zigzag-tape and Gurney-flaps. In addition, due to the special requirements of the project, a tilted TE (for smoother fitting into the blade shape) and a splitter plate (for reducing pressure drag) was investigated.

No	RN/10 ⁶	remark
13	2.75	Zigzag tape 0.125 mm
18	2.75	as 13
25	2.75	clean
45	2.75	VG2
73	2.75	GF 8 mm on PS
85	2.75	GF and splitter plate
88	2.75	VG2 and splitter plate
91	2.75	Splitter plate

Table 4: Explanation to selected polars. First 3 digits omitted, see Fig 26

As an important observation, it can be seen that all polars show real airfoil behaviour, despite of the profile's exceedingly high thickness. An explanation may lie in the observation that the flow behind the TE is more like of an airfoil with apparently more chord, see Fig. 27. Most important is a comparison of measurements against simulation. Global values c_L, c_D are seen in Fig 35.

6.4.1 Original TE

Polars 24398, 24400, 24402, 24411 and 24413 were recorded configured with straight (original) TE. When applied to a specific test turbine blade, Reynolds number is much larger (5 M instead of 2.7 M as in the wind tunnel test) for our numerical 3D set-up. As in the wind-tunnel test RN was increased from 1 M to 2.7 M, see Fig. 30, we do not expect adverse effects for higher RN.

6.4.2 Modified TE

As already written above, (see Figs 11 to 12) a smooth course of the trailing edge made it necessary to tilt it according to local twist (13°). A reduction in minimum drag was observed (0.097 → 0.090, making it even more favourable from the aerodynamic point of view.

Figure 26: Selected measured polars, compare to table 4

Figure 27: Velocity field from CFD at two AOAs - original TE

Figure 28: Pressure (coefficient) of clean configuration at 0° AOA. CFD vs measurement

Figure 29: Pressure (coefficient) of clean configuration at 6° AOA

Figure 30: RN variation for clean airfoil D60B-V5 measured in DWAA

Figure 31: View of geometrical shape of used VGs

	h(mm)	l(mm)	$\alpha/^\circ$	spacing (mm)	spacing of pairs (mm)	baseplate thickness (mm)
VG1	2.3	10	15	10	20	0.2
VG2	3.5	15	15	15	30	0.2
VG3	7	30	15	30	60	0.2

Table 5: Parameters of VGs

Figure 32: Overview of polars using three different arrangements of vortex generators

6.4.3 Vortex Generators

Fig 32 shows polars with three differently located VGs (vortex generators). Lift seems to be not much influenced (except for location 1, where cl_{max} goes down to 1 when compared to 1.5 in clean case).

1. $x/c = 0.15$
2. $x/c = 0.25/0.3$
3. $x/c = 0.3/0.45$

Table 6: Location of Vortex Generators

6.4.4 Gurney flaps

As for the case of VGs it is important to know to what amount these aerodynamical add-ons or devices may help on improving aerodynamic efficiency. Polars with Gurney flaps are shown in Fig 33. In contrast to VGs, GFs may increase lift but at the expense of (limited additional) drag.

6.4.5 Drag reduction by using a splitter-plate

As we have a very thick TE, a region of extended *dead-water* emerges, see Fig 34. Therefore the pressure there has pronounced - if not dominating - influence on the drag. Any device, which

Figure 33: Overview of polars using Gurney flaps

can be easily mounted and may reduce this under-pressure - is worth to be investigated. A splitter-plate [31] may reduce very low pressure ($c_p < -1$) regions by introducing some kind of deceleration.

This is valid at least for wake-flow behind cylinders and longer ($l \ll D$) plates. However, (see Fig 37) this seems not to be visible in (calculated) pressure distributions. Nevertheless, drag (Figs 35 and 36) seems to be reduced down to 0.05 (from 0.1). In addition, this can not be confirmed convincingly by CFD, see Fig. 35.

Fig 34 presents a general impression of the flow-field when using a splitter plate (compare to Fig 39). Figs 38 and 39b show more details.

Hucho [11] describes the effect of using splitter plates to influence the wake behind blunt bodies in somewhat more detail, but his observations (reduction of *base pressure*) remain largely the same.

Figure 34: Flow field (velocity magnitude) around airfoil with tilted trailing edge and splitter-plate (CFD)

Figure 35: Drag reduction by using a splitter plate, 2D-CFD results included, complete polar

Figure 36: Drag reduction by using a splitter plate, STD included. Columns 1 and 3 indicate values with and columns 2 and 4 without splitter plate. AOA = 0°

Figure 37: cp (pressure) distribution around complete airfoil - CFD results included

(a) no SP

(b) SP

Figure 38: Flow field around airfoil no SP (left) and with SP (right)

(a) Streamlines downstream from TE no splitter

(b) Streamlines downstream from TE with splitter plate

Figure 39: Comparison of streamline patterns without (left) and with splitter plate (right)

Figure 40: c_p (pressure) distribution around TE only. CFD results (line) and measurements (points). POL91 corresponds to arrangement using a splitter plate.

7 Discussion (all)

All results, as shown above seem to be consistent in the sense that our design approach has lead to a shape that shows (more or less) aerodynamic behaviour as predicted and/or expected. Nevertheless, predicting drag (reduction) and $c_{L,max}$ still is a challenge for (RANS-)CFD and depends heavily on the turbulence model used.

8 Summary and Conclusions (all)

A 60 %-thick airfoil for use in the inner part of a wind-turbine blade has been developed by using a variety of approaches: ranging from pure geometrical construction by providing a few number of characteristic quantities (like location of maximum thickness, shape of camber-line, TE thickness and so on) four different CFD codes (Xfoil, MSES, ANSYS-FLUENT and DLR's tau-code) has been used to define one single shape to be investigated in DWGE's wind tunnel at RN up to 2.75 million. Several configurations (clean, VG, GF, ZigZag-tape) were used. TE inclination was adapted for smoother variation in a blade and a splitter plate was additionally placed at the TE with the remarkable result of decreasing $c_{D,-min}$ down to ≈ 0.05 . A generic blade for a 10 MW turbine was defined (CIG10MW) and it could be shown that using the new developed profile (named D60B-V5) may lead to an increase of $c_{P,max}$ in the range of 4%, which would be a very high number. No indications for adverse 3D-effects are seen. A summary of this work has been submitted to a scientific journal [29] and is under review.

9 Abbreviations

AOA	Angle Of Attack (α)
APS	Alois Peter Schaffarczyk
B(A)L	Brandon (Arthur) Lobo
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CIG	China India Germany
DNW	Deutsch-Niederländische Windkanäle - German-Dutch Wind Tunnels
DWAA	Deutsche WindGuard aeroacoustic Wind Tunnel
DWGE	Deutsche WindGuard Engineering GmbH
drag counts	$10^4 \cdot c_D$
JS	Janick Suhr
lift-to-drag	Lift-to-Drag Ratio c_L/c_D
KSS	Korjahn Schlipf Schaffarczyk, own BEM code
M	million
NB	Nicholas Balaesque
RANS(E)	Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes (Equations)
RN	Reynolds Number
STD	STandard Deviation
TSR	Tip Speed Ratio (λ)
TE	Trailing Edge
TI	Turbulence Intensity
VK	Volker Kremer
c_L	Lift coefficient
c_p	Pressure coefficient
c_P	Power coefficient

Table 7: Abbreviations used in this report

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10 Appendix 1: Selected pressure distribution from wind tunnel entries and Flow Simulation

10.1 Original Trailing Edge

DLR-tau (TAU) simulations as well as wind tunnel tests (WT) were conducted at the same RN of 2 million.

10.2 Tilted Trailing Edge

FLUENT simulations are at RM = 3 million while the wind tunnel measurements were conducted at slightly lower RN of 2.75 million.

Figure 41: Original airfoil; $Re = 2 \times 10^6$

Figure 41: Continued: Original airfoil; $Re = 2 \times 10^6$

Figure 42: Tilted trailing edge; $Re = 3 \times 10^6$ (TAU) and $Re = 2.75 \times 10^6$ (Wind tunnel)

Figure 42: Continued: Tilted trailing edge; $Re = 3 \times 10^6$ (TAU) and $Re = 2.75 \times 10^6$ (Wind tunnel)

11 Appendix 2: List of investigated patents

Table 8: List of patents 1/2

Nr	Anmelder	Inhalt	Anmeldung	Relevant
DE 10 2012 110 711.4	GE	Rotorblatt Tooling Struktur	Nov 12	
DE 102 35 496 A1	GE	Rotorblatt Herstellung	Aug 02	
CN000211692705U	Goldwind	Cl-min control	Dez 18	
CN000211737379U	Goldwind	segmented blades		
EP000003734062A1	Goldwind	segmented blades		
CN000212671985U	Goldwind	some strengthened structure		
CN000211692705U	Goldwind	lighning protection		
EP 2 317 125 B1	Vestas	particular profile and airfoil	Feb 05	
EP 2 425 129 B1	Vestas	bewegliche Hinterkante	Mrz 10	
EP 2 983 882 B1	Vestas	A FIBRE PREFORM	Apr 14	
EP 3 601 782 B	Vestas	Ganze WT ?	Mrz 17	
EP 3 859 143 A1	Vestas	struktur	Dez 12	
EP 2 535 569 A2	Envision	partial pitch	Jun 12	
EP 2 728 170 B1	Envision	offset suction side	Okt 13	
DK 177928 B1	Envision	manufacturing method	Jun 13	
EP 2 816 227 B1	Envision	wie oben	Jun 13	
EP 2 975 259 A1	Envision	VGs	Jul 14	
EP 3 071 830 B1	Envision	wavy shaped TE	Okt 14	
EP 3 290 688 B1	Siemens	CONTROLLING ROTATIONAL SPEED	Aug 16	
	Siemens	BY CHANGING BLADE PROFILE		
EP 3 670 897 A1	Siemens	Multi Element in Aussenbereich !	Dez 18	
EP 2 447 527 B1	Windey	IPC	Jun 10	
EP 3 564 525 A1	CRRRC	Aufwind Turbine ?	Dez 16	
WO 2017/129691 A1	Wobben Prop	Dickes Profil mit "Rosendorn"	Jan 16	eventuell
DE 10 2013 210 901 A1	Wobben Prop	many details about aero design, $t < 40\%$	Jun 13	eventuell
DE 10 2018 103 732 A1	Wobben Prop	hat mit Profilen zu tun ist aber kryptisch	Feb 18	?
DE 10 2019 107 966 A1	Wobben Prop	Druckmessung	Mrz 19	
DE 10 2019 113 080 A1	Wobben Prop	Dicke Profile und "devices"	Mai 19	eventuell
DE 10 2019 113 085 A1	Wobben Prop	Dicke Profile und Gurney flap	Mai 19	ja
DE 10 2019 117 365 A1	Wobben Prop	serrations	Jun 19	
DE 10 2019 118 317 A1	Wobben Prop	serrations	Jul 19	
DE 10 2019 119 027 A1	Wobben Prop	Dickenrücklage, aerod. Entwurf	Jul 19	?
DE 198 15 519 A1	Tacke	Stall-strips , VGs wwohl nur für stall-Anlagen	Mrz 98	
EP 0 947 693 A2	Tacke	wie oben	Mrz 99	
DE 10 2008 052 858 B4	REpower	60%ige dicke flat-back profile	Okt 08	Ja
EP 2 321 105 B1	REpower	Blattfertigung	Apr 05	
DE 10 2005 014 884 B3	Nordex	Blattfertigung	Apr 05	
DE 10 2005 051 931 B4	Nordex	spezielle TE	Okt 05	
DE 10 2007 059 285 A1	Nordex	Mod. Nase im Innenbereich	Dez 07	
DE 10 2010 026 588 B4	Nordex	"optimierte Hinerkante"	Jul 10	
DE 10 2012 021 601 B4	Nordex	Formenheizung	Nov 12	
DE 10 2017 113 757 A1	Nordex	Pultriertes Profil	Jun 17	
DE 10 2017 113 762 A1	Nordex	Pultriertes Profil	Jun 17	
DE 10 2017 113 769 A1	Nordex	Pultriertes Profil	Jun 17	
DE 20 2013 007 886 U1	Nordex	abgekippt TE zur Lastreduktion	Sep 13	
EP 3 851 667 A1	Nordex	aero design of a WT blade	Jan 20	eventuell
		inside transitional region		
EP 2 337 950 B1	Senvion	wie DE 10 2008 052 858 B4	Sep 09	ja
EP 2 752 577 B	Senvion	Blattfertigung	Jan 11	
EP 3 147 499 A1	Senvion	Serrations	Sep 16	
DE 10 2016 110 295 A1	aerodyn Eng	nezzy tower profil	Jun 16	
WO 2012/083932 A2	aerodyn Eng	Blattfertigung	Dez 11	
WO 2017/206977 A1	aerodyn Eng	wie DE 10 2016 110 295 A1	Apr 17	
EP 2 593 670 B1	LM	aero design LM 40.3P und LM 42.1 P	Jul 10	

Table 9: List of patent2 2/2

EP 2 659 252 B1	LM	lastenmessung	Dez 11
EP 2 729 697 B1	LM	Allgemeiner Aufbau - völlig unklar was und warum	Jul 12
EP 2 809 499 B1	LM	Herstellungsverfahren	Jan 13
EP 3 027 893 B1 EP 3 183 102 B1	LM LM	Detail Blattfertigung Verfahren zum Formenbau	Jul 14 Aug 15
EP 3 360 670 A1	LM	Intrusion opt. Querschnitt	Feb 17
EP 3 431 754 B1	LM	Serrations	Feb 16
EP 3 488 100 B1	LM	Herstellungsverfahren für flat back TE	Jul 17
US 10,316,817 B2	LM	Herstellung Laminat in Form	Apr 15
WO 2018/015254 A1	LM	abgeschnittener Kreis als Nabenanschluss	Jul 16
DE 10 2011 050 777 A1	DeWind	Coning ?	Mai 11
WO 2012/164045 A1 EP 2 524 134 B1	DeWind Neptco	wie DE 10 2011 050 777 A1 Rotorblattfertigung	Mai 12 Jan 11
US 2105/0078911 A1	Neptco	Rotorblattfertigung	Okt 14
US 2015/0151390 A1	Neptco	PrePreg Bearbeitungsmaschine	Feb 15
DE 10 2007 036 536 A1	EADS	Sehr spezielles Profil (mE ungeeignet)	Aug 07
EP 2 025 928 A2	EADS	wie DE 10 2007 036 536 A1	Jul 08
DE 297 15 248 U1	ISET	Yaw Mechanismus	Aug 97
DE 10 2010 014 961 B4	Uni Bremen	Flexible Form für Blattfertigung	Apr 10
DE 10 2010 027 003 B4	Uni Ol	Vorflügel	Jul 10
DE 10 2011 076 082 B4	TU Chemitz	Rotorblattherstellung	Mai 11
DE 10 2011 110 280 A1	HS Bremen	(ungeeignetes) Flügelprofil	Jun 11
DE 10 2012 015 353 A1	Uni Ol FhG	irgendwas am Tip	Aug 12
DE 10 2016 224 877 A1	Uni Erlangen	Rotorblattlager	Dez 16
DE 10 2017 129 708 A1	cp.max	steuerbare Hinterkante	Dez 17
DE 10 2018 123 627 A1	BTU Cottbus	Strömungsprofilelement (so etwas wie Serrations)	Sep 18
DE 10 2019 215 150 A1	Uni Stuttgart	Laminarhaltung	Okt 19
EP 3 276 064 A1	TU Dresden	Sandwichkern	Jul 17
EP 2 998 572 B1	Best Blades GmbH	Anordnung von Flat back profilen	Sep 14
DE 10 2013 006 203 A1	HKB GmbH	(Holz)-Rotorblatt	Apr 13
DE 10 2011 118 844 B3	Sandrah Kreye	Vertikalanlage	Nov 11
0 364 020 B1	Josef Moser	Mischung aus Savonius	Sep 89
EP 2 610 482 A2	Andrey Temerov	Vertikalanlagenprofil	Nov 12
EP 3 318 750 B1	Caren Meicnic Teoranta	Turbine unbekannter Funktion	Nov 16
WO 2018/007403 A1	Peter Lutz	Rotordurchmesserergrößerung	Jul 17
CN000106270077A	Sandy Rools Inc	blade surface	
CN000205553268U	MingYang	connection structure for the segmented blade	
WO002021185263A1	Shanghai Electric	stringer reinforcement structure for the blade	
WO002013004125A1	windy	a self-protection method for the wind turbine	

12 Appendix3: Test matrix

DBU Dicke Profile

Date	run	Model	Re x 10% (-)	Tripping	VG Type	VG Location	Addons	Comments	Priority
10.07.		D60_V5_orig						Model installation finishing Pressure check	
11.07.	24398		1					Testruns Boundary layer controll tests (Corner Vjs. tufts)	0
	24400		2					Clean	1
	24402		2.75						1
12.07.	24411		4*					ZigZag tape 0.4mm @ 5505 PS10?	0
	24413		2 x			ZZ		ZigZag tape 0.125mm @ 5505 PS10?	1
	24413	D60_V5_newTE	2.75 x			ZZ		TE installation TE Pressure check	1
								Testruns	
								Clean	0
	24423+24421		4*					Clean	1
	24433		2						
	24425-24430		2.75						
	24431		2.75						
			4*					ZigZag tape 0.4mm @ 5505 PS10?	0
	24416		2 x			ZZ		ZigZag tape 0.125mm @ 5505 PS10?	1
	24418		2.75 x			ZZ			1
	24439		2.75		VG1	15 VG		Best VG position	1
14.07.	24445		2.75		VG2	25 VG			1
	24449		2.75		VG2	30 VG		diff. VG height	1
	24452		2.75		VG2	30 VG		High freq IR detection	1
	24453		2.75		VG3	30 VG		High freq IR detection	
	24454		2.75		VG3	30 VG		High freq IR detection	
	24456		2.75		VG3	45 VG			
	24458		2.75		VG3	45 VG			
17.07.	24666		2		VG1	30 VG		diff. VG height; Schnellpolare	
	24665		2.75		VG1	30 VG		diff. VG height	
18.07.	24473		2.75			Gurney 1		8 mm PS	
	24477		2.75			Gurney 2		8 mm PS & SS	
19.07.	24482		2.75		VG2	Gurney 1		8 mm PS+VG	
	24485		2.75		VG2	Gurney 1/Splitter		Gurney+Splitter plate length=TE thickness	
	24488		2.75		VG2	Splitter plate		Splitter plate length=TE thickness	
	24491		2.75			Splitter plate		Splitter plate length=TE thickness	
20.07.	34496		TBD					360 160deg Polare	
24.07.								Ausbau	

Figure 43: Test matrix for tunnel entry in July 2023